

Stacked Ternary Complexes of Salicylanilide, Dithionon and Tryptophan with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)

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Formation constants of ternary complexes of the types MAL^+ and MAL [where $M = Co(II), Ni(II)$ or $Cu(II)$, $A = dth(MAL^+)$ or $trp(MAL)$ and $L = trp(MAL^+)$ or $sal(MAL)$] have been determined in solution potentiometrically, to provide further evidence on complexation as a possible mode of action of fungicides. The formation tendency ($\Delta \log K_M$) of these complexes has been found to be positive for MAL^+ type of complexes which has been explained as being due to $M \rightarrow dth \pi$ -interaction and has also indicated intramolecular aromatic ring stacking between the ring systems of the two ligands. The negative values of $\Delta \log K_M$ have been found to be due to weak $M \rightarrow trp \pi$ -interaction and absence of intramolecular aromatic ring stacking.

It was observed in our previous investigation¹ that salicylanilide forms considerably stable complexes with some metal ions of biological interest, such as Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV), thereby supporting complexation as a possible mode of action of this fungicide. Since some specific structural requirements² are essential for the occurrence of complexation and also for a compound to show activity³, ternary complexes of salicylanilide (sal), dithionon (dth) and tryptophan (trp) with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) have been studied in solution to provide further evidence of complexation mechanism.

Experimental

Materials: The metal nitrates used were of A. R. grade. Salicylanilide was obtained from Boots Chemical, UK. Other chemicals were B.D.H. AnalaR grade. Dioxane was used after purification. A 70% aqueous dioxane (v/v) was chosen to keep salicylanilide, dithionon and their complexes in solution. All measurements were performed at constant ionic strength (0.1 M KNO_3) and constant temperature (25°).

Method: The binary systems were investigated with 1 : 2 molar ratio of metal ion and ligand while the ternary systems were studied in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of a metal ion, a primary ligand (trp or dth) and a secondary ligand (sal or trp) in acidic and non-acidic medium. The change in the pH of the solution, with each addition of 0.1 M NaOH solution was recorded with a Beckman pH meter equipped with a glass-calomel assembly. The pH values were corrected for 70% aqueous dioxane (v/v) medium using the method of Van Uitert and Haas⁴.

Calculations: The protonation constants and the stability constants (Table 1) of the parent binary complexes of sal and trp were calculated by computational methods of Irving and Rossotti⁵. Although most of the protonation and stability constants of parent binary complexes of trp are studied in aqueous medium^{6,7}, these were redetermined due to the change in medium of investigation. The stability constants of binary complexes of dth could not be calculated because evaluation of its protonation constant proved unsuccessful due to overlapping nature of the titration curves of ligand with or without mineral acid (HNO_3). It is

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY METAL COMPLEXES OF SALICYLANILIDE, TRYPTOPHAN AND DITHIONON IN 70% AQUEOUS DIOXANE (v/v); $\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$, $T = 25^\circ$.

Primary ligand	Secondary ligand	Metal Ion	$\log K_{MA}^M$	$\log K_{MA_2}^{MA}$	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	$\log K_{MAL}^M$	$\Delta \log K$
Trp	Sal	Co(II)	4.42	4.15	7.53	7.11	6.73	-0.80
		Ni(II)	5.51	5.10	7.72	7.35	6.82	-0.90
		Cu(II)	8.03	6.63	8.16	7.50	7.63	-0.53
Dth	Trp	Co(II)	—	—	4.42	4.15	4.77	+0.35
		Ni(II)	—	—	5.51	5.10	5.91	+0.40
		Cu(II)	—	—	8.03	6.63	8.71	+0.68

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not essential to know the stability constants of these complexes while calculating the stability constants of their ternary complexes as it was observed in the case of 2,2'-bipyridyl complexes⁹.

The stability constants of MAL⁺ type of complexes were calculated using the method of L'Heureux and Martell⁸ assuming dth as a primary ligand and trp as a secondary ligand because the nature of titration curve indicated the formation of 1:1, M-dth complex at very low pH which did not hydrolyse even at higher pH ~7. Some representative titration curves showing the sequence of addition of ligands and hydrolytic phenomenon are shown in Fig. 1. In MAL type of complexes trp has been considered as a primary ligand

Fig. 1. Representative potentiometric titration curves.
A: dth, B: 1:1; Cu(II)-dth, C: trp,
D: 1:1; Cu(II)-trp, E: 1:1:1, Cu(II)-dth-trp.

Fig. 2. Representative potentiometric titration curves.
A: HNO₃, B: HNO₃ + trp,
C: 1:1; Cu(II)-trp, D: 1:1:1, Cu(II)-trp-sal.

because 1:1 M-trp complex hydrolyses at higher pH value than 1:1 M-sal complex. Further, the

titration curve (Fig. 2) of 1:1:1 M-trp-sal runs slightly above the 1:1 M-trp curve, then superimposes and subsequently moves below it, thereby indicating the formation of 1:1:1 MAL complex after the complete formation of 1:1 M-trp complex. Hence, $K_{prim(trp)} K_{sec(sal)}$ is not an essential requirement in the formation of ternary complexes. Such observations have also been noticed by Gergely *et al*⁹ on the ternary complexes of α -amino acids. The stability constants of MAL complexes have been calculated using modified form of Irving-Rossotti method⁸ as employed by other workers¹⁰. These values have been listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems: The protonation and the stability constant values are more sensitive to the dielectric constant of the medium than to ionic strength or temperature. In dioxane-water mixtures of low dielectric constant, these values were expected to be significantly higher than those for the aqueous medium. But in the present investigation these values are not according to known general trend. It is evident from Table 1 that in the case of M-trp complexes the stability constant data in dioxane-water mixture are lower than those in water. Such irregularities have also been reported in literature^{6,7} on binary complexes of ligands containing N or N and O as donor atoms where the stability constants were generally found to be lower in solvents of low dielectric constants.

Ternary systems: All ternary systems revealed the formation of MAL⁺ or MAL type of complexes only. $\Delta \log K_M$ values (Table 1) are positive for MAL⁺ but negative for MAL complexes. The positive values of $\Delta \log K_M$ were found to be due to the discriminating properties of dth towards trp because in addition to $N \rightarrow M$ σ -bonding in dth complexes there also exist $M(d_{z^2} \rightarrow N(p))$ π -bonding. This renders the charge and electronegativity of the metal ion in M-dth complexes the same as in $[M(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$. These effects are not pronounced in the ternary complexes of trp containing mixed donor sites (N and O). Hence, the values of $\Delta \log K_M$ were found to be negative. Such results have also been observed by Sigel and Griesser¹¹. The positive values of $\Delta \log K_M$ may also be due to the absence of coulombic repulsion between two dissimilar ligand bound to the same metal ion and the negative values are due to smaller coulombic attraction of secondary ligand (sal).

It is evident from the above discussion that the ternary complexes are stabilized by several factors. Besides these factors, intramolecular aromatic ring stacking also plays an important role in increasing the stability constants of ternary complexes¹². Dithionon is a rigid as well as a good π -acceptor molecule while the ring system of trp is attached to a flexible side chain. Both of these ligands, when coordinated to the same metal ion, produce intramolecular aromatic ring stacking between the

aromatic ring systems of the two ligands. It is possible because the ring system of trp may reach easily to the rigid aromatic ring system of dth to produce these interactions. Such effects are less remarkable in the ternary complexes of sal and trp, because the ring system of sal is not rigid and there remains a freely hanging phenyl ring having no functional group that might involve in bonding. A tentative structure of stacked ternary complex of MAL^{2+} has been shown in Fig. 3. These results find

Fig. 3. A tentative structure of stacked ternary MAL^{2+} complex.

further support from the work of Sigel *et al*^{15,16} on the intramolecular hydrophobic interactions in ternary complexes of some aliphatic amino acids and ring stacking in ternary complexes of some aromatic amino acids. Similar results were also observed in our previous investigation on the stacked ternary complexes of some plant auxins involving 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline as primary ligands¹⁷.

On the basis of considerably high stability constants of binary and ternary metal complexes reported here, the metal ions which are vital constituent of various enzymes may interact with fungicides forming binary complexes which are further converted into ternary complexes involving tryptophan. Thus, all the enzymatic equilibria are disturbed and the conversion of tryptophan into various products is inhibited causing growth regulation.

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